

A Study of Latest Trends in the Indian Banking

Surekha Eknath Brahmkar¹, Dr. M.S. Deshpande²

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, KGDM Arts, Commerce & Science College, Niphad.

² Professor, School of Commerce & Management Sciences, SRTMU, Nanded.

Corresponding author- Surekha Eknath Brahmkar

Abstract

The Financial sector, of which Banking sector is the largest player, plays a dominant role in building the economy of an individual as well as a nation. Banks have control over a large part of the supply of money in circulation. They are the main stimulus for the economic progress of a country. Indian banking system touches the lives of millions of people and it is growing at a fast pace. Banking industry in India is facing number of challenges like changing needs and perceptions of customers, new regulations from time to time and great advances in technologies. The pressure of meeting these challenges have compelled banks to change the old ways of doing business. With the emergence of Privatisation, Globalisation and Liberalisation in India, Banks are focusing on Research and Development and applying various innovative ideas and technology. There is a close relationship between the development of banking sector and the new innovations in technology and Electronic data processing. The present paper focuses on major technology trends and innovation in banking.

Key Words: Banking sector, Growth, Economic development, Technologies, Privatisation, Globalisation.

Introduction

The banking industry in India has a huge canvas of history, which covers the traditional banking practices right from nationalization to privatization of banks and now to multinational banks in India. Therefore, Banking in India has been through a long journey. Banking industry in India has also achieved a new height with the changing times. The use of technology has brought a revolution in the working style of the banks. However, with the changing dynamics, banking business has brought a new kind of risk exposure. Majority of the banks are successful in keeping with the confidence of the customers as well as other stakeholders but not all the banks are able to live up to the expectation of them. In order to grow and gain the faith of stakeholders, organizations should try to improve the long-term financial performance and create wealth for the stakeholders.

We are currently in a phase of 'Digital Darwinism', an era where technology and society are evolving. The bang of digital forces like Social Media, Mobile, Analytics, Cloud and Internet of Things (IOT) are creating flow of business information in a more direct and cost efficient manner. India is not un-touched by this phase of 'Digital Darwinism'. The new technology trends such as Cloud Computing, Artificial Intelligence and Biometrics etc, are likely to bring about significant changes in the way payments would be processed in the future. Already the Indian banking sector is making substantial investment in forming digital infrastructure to offer various solutions like mobile banking, e-wallets and virtual cards, etc. Payment Systems have paved the way for New Banking Paradigms by bringing new financial technology driven instruments with customer's satisfaction and risk mitigation techniques. Technology that is driven by innovation and its

ability to design new products and services is dynamic and hard to predict precisely. One would not have thought about making transactions in simple touches, but technology has made it possible. Today, mobility and customer ease are viewed as the basic factors of growth and banks are continually evolving with new technology. Markets for banks are completely customer driven and hence technology needs to be customer centric ease of use and safety of transactions. Technology thus plays an enabler role in providing a win-win tool for both the banks and their customers.

Objectives of the Study

i. To study the recent trends in banking sector

Data Collection

The study is descriptive in nature and is based on secondary data. The data are collected from various reports, journals, news articles, various bank portals, RBI portal and internet sources.

Structure of Indian Banking Sector

In our country we are having a well-developed and significant banking system with different classes of banks- public sector banks, foreign banks, private banks- both old and new generation banks, regional rural banks and cooperative banks in the leadership of RBI. The banks are set up in the supervision of different committees created by the Government with the aim to bring about operational flexibility and functional autonomy to enhance efficiency, productivity, profitability of banks. Earlier the finance function was carried down by the Sahukars, moneylenders and they creates a lot of difficulty level to individuals. Their rate of interest differs from person to person and impose different unusual condition from borrower to borrower. Then a need arise to having legalized and systemic process for lending and deposit the funds and this solve out the problems of the individuals. After that banks have

classified according to their proper uses i.e private, public, foreign and regional rural banks to provide benefits to every sector of society. Competition in banking sector brings various challenges before the banks such as product positioning, innovative ideas and channels and new market trends. Banks are restricting their administrative folio by converting manpower into machine power.i.e, banks are decreasing manual powers and getting maximum work done through machine power.

Recent Trends in Banking Sector

1. Internet

Internet is a network of computers. Through internet the process of dealing customer is getting very fast and banking can be used at anytime, anywhere. It works as global trend through which distance and time can be reduced to perform the transaction. IT services have enabled innovation and hi-tech services to make the complication and concern of original banking plan to much easier and easily accessible by the consumers and at present the trend has a rise to carry out the transactions through mobile banking, direct bill payment, electronic fund transfer and the I-banking.

Most of the large banks in industry offers fully secure and functional online banking at free of cost. The public can now check and control their money in a safest way for customers it is the realization of their anywhere, anytime, anyway banking dreams

2. Atm

An automated teller machine is an electronic banking outlet that allows customers to know about their basic transaction without any bank representative. Atms can access through a credit or debit card. There are 2 types of ATM functions. Basic type allows customers to withdraw cash and receive reports only and more complex type accept deposits and provide more advanced features.

The person who is having account in any bank can use their bank's ATM at free of cost but through any other bank will incur a small fee. This facility is provided to the customers 24 hours a day. For use ATM facility customer should have a ATM card .this is a plastic card, magnetically coded. Each card holder can use their card through a secret personal identification number. This is issued for security purpose.

3. Mobile Banking

It is a service provided by the particular bank to the customer to avail service through their registered mobile number. The facility only is available on registered number and the number which is linked to aadhar number of the customer. it usually available on a 24 hour basis like ATMs. Transaction through mobile banking depends on the banking application provided by the particular bank. The services are

electronic bill payment , remote cheque deposits, p2p payment etc.

Mobile banking services are; Mini statement & alert on account activity Access to loan statement Fund transfer Bill payments

4. Electronic Payment and Settlement System

Payment & settlement system in India is mainly for financial transaction. These are covered by the act of payment & settlement system Act, 2007 and its regulated by RBI. In India, multiple systems are used for gross and net settlement. To provide safety and security to customers RBI is providing its best payment system & makes the whole process easier for banks. Through IT system the banking sector has been growing successfully and implement electronic payment to enhance the banking systems.

- **RTGS:** It stands for real time gross settlement . when settlement and transfer takes place on a real time and on gross basis then RTGS is used i.e transfer of money from one bank to another bank on a real time & gross basis. Real time means there is not any waiting period in settlement and gross settlement means the transaction is settled on one to one basis without bunching with any transaction. Fee for RTGS differ from bank to bank. Customer can avail the RTGS facility between 9 AM to 4:30 PM on weekdays and 9AM to 2:00 PM on Saturday. However the timing for RTGS vary from bank to bank.
- **NEFT:** This facility was provided in Nov. 2005. This system is a nationwide system that allows individuals, firms and corporation to transfer their funds electronically from any bank branch to any individual, firm or corporate having an account with any other bank branch in the country. It is done through electronic message.
- **Electronic clearing service:** This system was introduced in 1990 by the RBI. ECS payment are used for bulk transfers and repetitive payments like salary, interest, dividend payments. This transfer takes place through a proper mechanism i.e clearing houses. Settlement is done on a t+1 basis.
- **ECS (credit):** This works on the principle of single debit multiple credit and is used for repetitive payments like salary.
- **ECS (debit):** This service works on the principle of single credit multiple debit and is used by utility service providers for collection of bills and charges.

Conclusion

An upgradation of technology banks are playing vital role in economic development. Banking sector in India is resulting with increased growth in customers. By providing innovative

facilities of banks. The changes made by banks are mostly focused on financial inclusion for expansion into rural areas and bringing stability by boosting credit growth making banking services near to the customer directly and reducing customer valuable time. The current trends in banking are building blocks of the “Cashless Economy”. Though there are few challenges, technology will keep evolving and with collaborative efforts of Banks, Government and end users, overcoming these challenges will certainly be possible. The initiative of Government of India will very soon achieve its mission and rural India too would be “digitally literate”. Banks will have to develop a strategy to bridge the gap of technology in rural banks and urban banks. Today, Indian banking industry is on the threshold of “next generation banking”. ICT innovation clubbed with dream of “cashless economy” will certainly bring about metamorphosis in the banking sector.

References

1. Ayachit Madhura (2016) “ICT Innovation in Indian Banking Sector: Trends and Challenges”, IOSR, Journal of Business and Management, PP 21-27.
2. Sujatha, Haritha, Sreeja (2017) “A study on recent trends of banking sector in india”, Mahratta chamber of commerce, Pune(India), PP 296-303.
3. Banking Technology present status and future trends (2017), report present by Institute for Development and Research in Banking Technology.
4. Gupta, Arya, Goel (2017) “Emerging trends in banking sector in India (With Special Reference to Digitization)”, International Journal of Science Technology and Management, Vol-6 issue -03, PP 260-268.
5. Syan (2018) “Emerging trends in banking sector in India (With Special Reference to Digitization)”, Abhinav Publication, Vol-7 issue-1, PP 76-81.
6. Anbalagan (2017) “New Technological Changes in Indian Banking Sector”, International Journal of Scientific Research and Management, Vol-05 issue-09, PP 7015-7021.
7. Yajurvedi (2015) “Emerging Trends in Banking-Increasing Role of Information Technology”, Indian journal of applied research, Vol-05 issue-10, PP 636-639.